

SOCIAL SCIENCES

REALIZATION OF THE PRINCIPLE OF JUSTICE DURING THE PANDEMIC OF COVID-19 IN SRI LANKA

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic is not merely a public health emergency, it goes far beyond that: it encompasses economic crisis, social crisis, and a human crisis that is rapidly turning into a human rights crisis. The WMA Declaration of Lisbon on the Rights of the Patient reads that the interests of everyone should be taken into consideration and ensures that no one should be left behind. Human rights-based action can help beat the pandemic by putting everyone's health at the forefront. This is written in the official document, the life experience shows the opposite situation: COVID-positive patients are a priority, whilst other patients are deprived of the right to undergo routine medical check-ups that results in severe complications and irreversible consequences leading to deaths.

Keywords: COVID, pandemic, patients, diseases, justice.

COVID-19 has been a brutal reminder of the importance of ensuring lasting progress with respect to social right's enjoyment, particularly through the development of the universal public health care services and the adherence of the people to it.

The pandemic sows in practical terms the indivisibility of human rights – giving rise to the major ethical challenges and difficult decisions made in counteracting them, one of which is the highly debated criticism of the principle of justice!

As we all know and have studied, the principles of justice denoting equality, fairness and access are one of the first virtues of social institutions as truth is of systems of thought. But, the question is- Were these virtues realized as said in theory in the practical aspects of the pandemic? Let me take you in a journey of pros and cons to actually visualize and idealize the above set question.

Firstly, the COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in serious lockdowns causing restriction of liberties; refuse to medical treatment, inability of access to the minimum of the daily essentials a citizen requires for one's survival and many other changes to everyday patterns of behavior in persons.

Lockdowns cut off most of what people yearned for in the height of the pandemic, even if they did get access to their needs, it was not easy and had many obstacles to overcome

The justice issue it raises are diverse and profound and are not confined to just one aspect of the health care sector or even to the health care sector only, but disseminates vastly among other institutions as well and this will demand our attention for a very long time.

Out of many questions one of the most questioned or rather considered as a central issue is the newly introduced "COVID-19 triage" in hospitals and its utilization of ICU's, hospital beds, medicine, supplies and so on and so forth

The current situation has led to new systems that are required given the circumstances but was it necessary that we disregard the old measures or as they claim "not important as of now", this brought on more chaos as patients criticized and argued with the officials.

Patients complained of how they were treated even if they were not on the brink of death as surviving and were made to wait in queues that lasted hours and maybe even days, gotten their appointments cancelled or postponed with no further notices raising questions and judgments- Are all patients treated fairly? As equals? Aren't patient's unrelated to COVID patients too? Do all patients receive the same access as those infected ones?

This lead to conflicts amongst patients, those who came with minimum symptoms worsened over time due to lack of access or proper consultation and led eventually to unavoidable deaths which could have been prevented if they had been noticed earlier.

Dire situations were not only the cases in hospitals but also in other related facilities such as detention centers, psychiatric hospitals, social care homes, newly established quarantine facilities or zones. These places required patients to move freely about, distress have consultations with specialized doctors or even meet their loved ones for the sake of their physical and mental stability and well-being but, COVID deprived them of such liberties.

Resulting from such issues there was an unfortunate incident in Sri Lanka where a disabled boy of just 25 years committed suicide as his mother was forcibly taken into treatment leaving the child helpless and depressed/ it is devastating yet true and reality as the new realities required new norms which weren't available, leaving officials burdened and speechless as to how to provide care and treatment to the special needs groups.

Therefore, at this point it is necessary to stress that even the lives saved seemed to be in tension with equity! All the hard work seemed to turn into dust due to harsh criticism from all around.

Moreover a central point to this discussion and research is the utilization of ICUs. It was declared by the health ministries that the ICU importance is for COVID-19 patients, leaving staff of other departments and its patients requiring this essential service for survival helpless, speechless, hopeless questioning how much weight is given for the equality of access. This deprived of youth with a more survival rate lose their dreams of the future into the darkness while cor-morbid senior posterities were given the chance to see another day of light.

Not only were the general everyday patients in conflict, the COVID-19 patients had their own issues to deal with amidst all the attitude and stigma the society had classified them into – it was known in my country that it was a curse or bad karma that acted upon such people and wished that they'd perish not accounting that they were as innocent as all the others are.

Also, most of the infected patients were sent and contained in clusters to the quarantine centers and their cure seemed far off until recently with the introduction of the vaccines.

And when it comes for organ transplantation the COVID positive patients were not offered a position in the list as the disease was novel and was not proven that a transplant could increase their survival or even rather save them.

Another potential issue that aroused after the light of the vaccines was the immunity passports, immense resentment arose among those who did not hold such credibility; this caused a loss of social cohesion.

While all these opposing factors existed all nations worldwide came together with services extending from the WHO to the regional health care sectors of each country.

In Sri Lanka guidelines were developed as one vision “DREAM” on the social distancing guidelines and provision of essential healthcare, medicine were delivered via post even while clinics remained closed.

The Tele-Health program was introduced, promoted and regulated where patients could access their doctors by just the click of a button, home visits were expanded, volunteer groups initiated social campaigns and carried out odd-jobs to raise awareness and help with the division of labour.

Primary medical care units, OPD, emergency and accident care units, maternity clinics operated 24 hours following the new social distancing regulations. Such services were distributed among both the national and private medical facilities giving rise to more access and more resources to patients.

Right now Sri Lanka is continuing the vaccination programs to offer hope to better future and a new method of infection control.

Finally it can be concluded that amidst all challenges – the scope of equity was somewhat achieved to encompass remediable differences among social, economic, demographic or geographic groups during the COVID-19 allowing people to look beyond differences in lives of the pandemic, because “United we stand, divided we fall”.

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